

ISLAMIZATION AND INTERNATIONALIZATION FOR SUSTAINABILITY OF FAITH-BASED MUSLIM UNIVERSITIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

In line with the alarming rate at which private higher institutions have sprung up in Nigeria recently, competition amongst such institutions become inevitable. Such competitions become more spelled out in the numerous ranking strategies adopted to assess institutions globally. What then can the Islamic universities do to make a difference? While healthy rivalry is a welcome development, the fact remains that the existing Islamic universities need to adopt a new measure of assessing themselves to compete effectively with others. To sustain these institutions, we suggest Islamization and internationalization as alternative options. Our conviction of this is that the majority of the students in these institutions are Muslims, while Muslims constitute a large percentage of the administrative staff. It will therefore be a dis-service to the community if their operation does less in the Islamization programme, while internationalization is expected to be explored to make them relevant in the Muslim world and at the global level. The paper concludes that the Islamization programme needs to be adopted holistically by the existing Islamic universities, while internationalization will enhance the attainment of core Islamic values and assist effective global competition.

Keywords: Islamization, internationalization, Faith-based, Universities

Introduction

Right from its inception, the acquisition of knowledge is given prominence by Islam. It is therefore not surprising that the first revelation to the Prophet Muhammad was on reading and the use of pen. The Prophet did not hesitate to put this into action, as he taught his companions what was revealed to him. His companions further extended the scope of their knowledge beyond religious education as they acquired the available knowledge, they came in contact with under the Prophetic guidance that knowledge has no geographical delineation. It is acknowledged that Muslims who did not relent in acquiring knowledge later emerged as leaders in all available brands of knowledge, particularly in mathematics, geography, history, philosophy, medicine

and logic. The historic *Baytul Hikmah* established during the Abbasid period attested to the seriousness of Muslims in acquiring all available knowledge of the period. The establishment of some early universities was also attributed to Muslims. The Nizamiyyah University in Baghdad and Al-Azhar University in Cairo were established as far back as 1066/67CE (Nakosteen, 1964). The Muslims' active contributions to knowledge later suffered a setback due to political turmoil and tumults as well as their complacency. They lost the battle to the West who consequently separated divine knowledge from what they called human sciences. They further confused Muslim education by commissioning non-Muslims to delve into Islam to distort and misrepresent Islam so that the intellectual community was not

attracted to it. To conclude their plot against Islam, the Muslim world was colonized and the distorted type of knowledge was represented to them.

The suppression of the Muslim world by the colonialists forced the Muslims to withdraw from the academic and intellectual breakthroughs which they were known for before. They withdrew themselves to a sort of 'Islamic' education that only dealt with the Qur'anic sciences and jurisprudence forgetting that the so-called human sciences are part and parcel of Islamic education. Since then, Muslims have been sticking to reading the Qur'an as if they are glued to it, and the Glorious Book remains the most-read book in the world. However, this reading does not transcend going through pages of the book, as they read it without contemplating the text and message of the book. Therefore, *tilawah* has not been translated into *tadabbur* of the book. Muslims reduce themselves to futuristic eschatological matters that have no direct bearing on *Imān* and to making the earth peaceful to live. They dissipated energy on the coming of Jesus Christ and Masih Dajjal (Anti-Christ), as if such discourses have any positive effect on the Muslim community, and as if such beliefs are fundamental pillars of faith in Islam. When the Western world is busy exploring space and evolving technological devices, the Muslim world concentrates on waging wars against itself, condemning its multifarious ideologies. While a group is eulogizing the growth of beards as part of the Prophet's *sunnah*, another group faces condemnation of the use of the rosary on the basis that the Prophet did not use any but fingers to count. Trivial issues polarize the *Ummah* that the centre could no longer hold. Rather than finding means of exploring nature for human benefits using the template of the Qur'an, scholars embark on spending hours looking for evidence on the mode of greeting. Instead of reacting to the Qur'anic

call to penetrate space, and study animals and other creatures, Muslims are sweating on issues that are of no direct benefit to mankind. The Qur'an therefore becomes the lamp in the hand of a blind Muslim. Whereas the lamp is not beneficial to the blind, those beside him benefit from the light. Lamenting on the deplorable situation of the Muslims, Muhammad (1989) writes:

It would appear to me that many Muslims have accepted and to some extent have taken pride in their ignorance with unbelievable satisfaction. We are in acute social, economic and political agony, yet many Muslims have adopted a strangely false sense of security: reading the Qur'an will bring them *thawab* or blessings even if they do not understand or practice it; going out on *tabligh* or propagation will secure a piece of paradise; writing pamphlets and propaganda sheets will win support for Islam...

Unsatisfied with the backwardness of the Muslims in all spheres of life, some concerned Muslim scholars and thinkers started calling on the *Ummah* in their writings and speeches to wake from their slumber and reform their education system to bail them out of their backwardness. One of the means through which the Muslims responded to this call is by establishing schools and colleges to bring back to such schools true Islamic education and writing and discussing science from a true-believing perspective. Among such reformers was Syed Ahmad Khan who felt unsatisfied with the condition of the Muslim *Ummah* in his country and therefore sought remedy in the reformation of the Islamic educational system by establishing Aligarhi Muhammadan School in 1875. In the same vein, Jamal ad-Din Al-Afghani advocated for a *Darul-Funun*, a new university devoted to the teaching of modern sciences. The establishment of universities in Nigeria could also be seen as

a good development, as these institutions are meant to pursue Islamic goals. It is on this note that this paper is expected to provide more insight into how these universities could sustain the spirit of Islam by reforming their curriculum through the Islamization of the knowledge programme and as well internationalise the institutions to compete favourably with other institutions of world-class.

Islamization of Knowledge Programme: Historical Antecedents

The foundation of Islamization was laid by the Prophet who reformed the pre-Islamic Arab practices and transformed them in all facets of life. His companions, particularly the Rightly-Guided caliphs sustained this step of the Prophet. The process of Islamization was further expanded during the Abbasid period when the *Baytul Hikmah* was established. This enhanced Muslims' breakthroughs in all the available intellectual fields of the period and also imparted this to Western Europe. This laudable achievement prompted Brifeld (cited by Qutb, 1975) to conclude that "there is not a particular aspect of the European blossoming whose origin cannot safely be ascribed to the influence of Islamic culture." The eventual fall of the Muslim empire and the havoc of the Crusaders and Moguls however erased the Muslims' achievements from the memory of people, while the colonization of the Muslim world succeeded in corrupting the Muslim education system.

Unsatisfied with the crisis in the Muslim education system, some attempts were made by Muslims to save knowledge from distortion. A sort of what Sultan (1997) described as 'partial Islamization' was thus undertaken by some scholars like Jamal- ad- Din al-Afghani (d. 1897), Hassan al-Banna (d. 1949), Rashid Ridha (d1955), Sayydi Qutb (d. 1966) and Allama Muhammad Iqbal, all who made remarkable contributions towards having a

comprehensive and dynamic concept of Islamization of education in their speeches and writings.

The urge to restore a pure Islamic education system became a global issue in 1977 when the First World Conference on Muslim Education was held in Makkah, Saudi Arabia. From there, the term Islamization of Knowledge was adopted as a veritable means of bringing Islamic education back to its normal axis. More than eight similar conferences of the same magnitude have been held on Islamic education since then. In addition, many conferences on Islamization of Knowledge have been organized in different countries. These conferences have been successful to a large extent as they assisted in formulating educational aims and objectives and have led to the rise of educational and intellectual institutions and organizations. Such include the establishment of the International Institute of Islamic Thought (IIIT) in Herndon, Virginia in 1981; the World Centre for Islamic Education in Makkah under the auspices of the Organization of Islamic Conference (OIC); the Islamic Academy in the United Kingdom in 1983 and the Darel Ihsan Trust at Bangladesh in 1986. Others are the Institute of Islamic Science and Technology (IIIST) in 1987 in Washington DC; the International Institute of Islamic Thought and Civilization (ISTAC) in Malaysia by Syed Naquib al-Attas; the Institute of Islamic Education and Research in Bangladesh in 1981; and the International Board of Education Research and Resources (IBERR) founded in 1993 in South Africa (Adebayo, 2003).

One of the outcomes of such conferences was the establishment of International Islamic universities in Islamabad, Dhaka, Kuala Lumpur, Niger and Uganda to implement the Islamization of the knowledge programme at the higher education level and to promote research in various aspects of Islamic education. In

Nigeria, quite a good number of universities were equally established by Muslim individuals and organizations. Such are Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin; Crescent University, Abeokuta; Katsina (now Al-Qalam) University, Katsina; Fountain University, Osogbo; and Summit University, Offa. Since these universities were established to create an Islamic environment for proper Islamic education to thrive, and for the curriculum to be enriched with Islamic values, it becomes imperative for these institutions to adopt the Islamization programme.

Modalities for Islamizing knowledge in Muslim universities

The term Islamization of knowledge has been defined differently by different scholars. According to Al-Alwani (1995), it is “a methodological issue prepositioned on the identification and articulation of the relationship between revelation and real existence.” Shehu (1998) sees it as an attempt to reorient and recast knowledge to conform to the Islamic belief system and worldview. A more comprehensive definition was given by Sulaiman (2000) who defines it as “an attempt through which those aspects of the body and purpose of knowledge and of the process and methodologies of discovering, validating, imparting and applying it which oppose Islam, are identified and made subservient to the Islamic worldview.” Not minding the use of words in the definitions of the concept of Islamization, they all tend towards Muslims’ consciousness of dichotomy in knowledge as presented by the West and Muslims’ adoption of *Wahyi* knowledge at the expense of *Duniyawi* knowledge. The definitions also see the process and methodologies of imparting and acquiring knowledge to be against the spirit of Islam, hence the imperative for its Islamization. The definitions also inform that acquisition of knowledge is compulsory for Muslims to acquire, but

such should be properly scrutinized to avoid absorbing un-Islamic ones into Islam, without being Islamized. This informs why Al-Faruqi frowned at the alienation of *wahy* and ‘*aql*’ from each other, but rather to unify the two in such a way that every discipline is remoulded “to incorporate the relevance of Islam along the triple axis constitutive of *tawhid*” (Al-Faruqi, 1988). To achieve the Islamization objectives, Al-Faruqi formulated a twelve-step work plan. These are:

1. Mastery of the modern disciplines
2. Detailed survey of disciplines
3. Mastery of the Islamic Legacy: The Anthology
4. Mastery of the Islamic Legacy: The Analysis
5. Establishment of the specific relevance of Islam to the disciplines
6. Critical assessment of the modern disciplines
7. Critical assessment of the Islamic legacy
8. Survey of the *Ummah*’s major problems
9. Survey of the problems of humankind
10. Creative analysis and synthesis
11. Recasting the disciplines under the framework of Islam: The University Textbooks
12. Dissemination of the Islamized knowledge (Al-Faruqi, 1988).

The above work plan of Al-Faruqi has been exposed to serious criticism by scholars. That notwithstanding, the critics of the work plan only succeeded in compressing the steps to ensure their reduction. In short, Al-Faruqi has succeeded in putting down a template for achieving the goals of Islamization. The relevance of the work plan is that every Muslim university is expected to key into it so that they can justify the purpose of establishing the institutions. Adebayo (2011) has also identified some

Islamization approaches adopted in some Muslim minority countries. Such include:

1. The substitute approach: This is a situation where a course offered in the Department of Islamic Studies is substituted in lieu of the course in other social sciences departments.
2. Adjunct approach: This involves the introduction of supplementary readings from the Islamic viewpoint to add to courses in existing secular curricula; e.g. trying to understand the concept of democracy and sovereignty from the perspective of Islam.
3. The source approach: This has to do with sourcing for references from the Qur'an during the course of teaching a particular course or concept.
4. The relational approach: This is a method of relating scientific and technological concepts to the Qur'an and *sunnah*.
5. Tributary approach: This is where tributes are paid to Muslim scientists who have made landmark achievements in the field of sciences.
6. Critical review approach: This has to do with attempting to correct the heresies of non-Muslim scholars through the scholastic and critical appraisal of their submissions.

A critical appraisal of each of the approaches has been done by Adebayo (2011) in favour of Omar Kasule (2001) who considered these as wrong approaches to the Islamization of knowledge programme because they did not address the core issues of the paradigms and methodology of disciplines. That notwithstanding, each of these approaches may still be relevant to a Muslim university that has not bailed herself out of the Western worldview and has not gotten her bearing in the Islamization programme. A university cannot boast of being an Islamic

university if it has not taken Islamization as a serious programme. It is on this basis that Al-Attas (cited by Wan Daud, 1998) submitted that “unless we can formulate all basic concepts of knowledge from the point of view of Islamic metaphysics, we shall not be able to establish an Islamic university.” For a Muslim university to graduate from an Islamic university, therefore, Islamization of her programmes of activities becomes imperative. This can however be enhanced if it adopts internationalization for cross-fertilization of ideas with other Islamic universities worldwide. Its interaction with conventional universities can also assist in accelerating Islamization programme when it discovers the extent of westernization and hegemonization of these universities and so decides to adopt Islamization to avoid blind imitation of the conventional universities.

The concept of Internationalization

The wave of globalization ushered in a new way of doing things in all facets of life; what seemed to have been impossible is now possible with the exploration of cyberspace. This limitless opportunity for man to traverse and explore the universe explains the divine injunction that encourages Jinn and mankind to attempt passing beyond the regions of the heavens and the earth. Man, thus sees beyond his nose, aspiring to know what is not only within his environment but also what is beyond. One of the outcomes of globalization therefore is the concept of internationalization – a term not only common in academia but also among those in government and other international organizations. In the view of Mitchell and Nielsen (undated):

The institution of higher education has always been international in scope with the exchange of ideas, scholars and students, but modern technology, the internet,

communication technologies, the increasing flow of students and highly educated scientists from all over the world as well as scientific investment, patent activities and R & D make globalization more visible in the scientific field today (cdn.intechopen.com/pdfs/38270/inTech_internationalization_and_globalization_in_higher_education).

According to Knight (1997), globalization is the ‘flow of technology, economy, knowledge, people, values and ideas across borders’, while internationalization of higher education is ‘one of the ways that a country responds to the impact of globalization yet, at the same time respects the individuality of the nation’. In this wise, she defines internationalization as “the process of integrating an international or intercultural dimension into the teaching, research, and service functions of the institution.” This definition was later modified by her as “the process of integrating an international, intercultural, or global dimension into the purpose, functions or delivery of postsecondary education.” The term internationalization, according to Grant Harman (2004), is often used to refer to the international movement of students and staff between countries; internationalization of higher education curricula; international links for research and open learning programmes; and bilateral, regional, and international recognition of higher education qualifications. Internationalization is therefore a process of increasing cooperation and interconnectedness between institutions of different nations. However, according to De Wit (2011), it is a misconception to assume that internationalization means teaching in English, studying abroad, or teaching an

international subject. It does not equally mean having many international students.

It can be said that the foundation of the internationalization of education was laid by the Muslims. This can be attested to their seriousness in traveling out to study ancient Greek and Roman sciences and later translating these works into the Arabic language. The spirit of acquiring foreign sciences became a public concern during the hegemony of the Abbasid Dynasty (749-1258 CE), especially during the time of Khalifah Abu Ja‘far Al-Mansur (754-775 C.E). The development of the translation became more internationalized during the reign of another Abbasid Caliph called Ma‘mun (813-833C.E) who realized the value of Greek works, and hence organized the work of translation on a large scale. He made all possible efforts to collect whatever was available of Greek works and to keep the same in his domain. Ma‘mun further internationalized knowledge by ordering the Byzantine emperor Michael III to collect all essential Greek works in his domain and bring them to Baghdad. He also sent emissaries to all other parts of the Muslim empire to collect the available Greek works. He further expanded the *Baytu al-hikmah* (The House of Wisdom) by enlarging the translation bureau and raising it into a great academy for study and research. It is said to be an academy of a university standard of today. He also employed the service of non-Muslims in the translation activities of foreign works into Arabic language. Among the translators of philosophical materials into Arabic during Al-ma‘mun was Yahya al-Badr. He translated the major works of Aristotle into Arabic. Costa son of Luke was in charge of Greek and Syrian works. Under him, the books of Plato, Aristotle, Galen, Euclid, Archimedes and Ptolemy were translated into Arabic. Duban was in charge of translating Sanskrit books, Mathematics, Astronomy and others into the Arabic Language. Yahya ibn Harun was charged

with the responsibility of translating the ancient Persian works into Arabic. Hunayn bn. Ishaq (809-873C.E) was charged with the scientific translation of the works collected in the *Baytul-Hikmah*. He was a medical doctor and so a court physician to the Caliph. The Muslims therefore pursued the sciences with profound application and they later started disseminating knowledge internationally by establishing institutions of learning in a vast number of cities.

The need for Internationalization of Muslim universities

Without mincing words, there are numerous challenges confronting Muslim universities in Nigeria. However, joint and well-coordinated efforts will help in no small measure to address and overcome the challenges of higher education in this increasingly competitive and globalized era. An attestation to this was given by the Vice-Chancellor of Muslim University of Morogoro, Tanzania, Professor Hamza Mustafa Njozi (2015) that at the inception of the University, there was no model in the country from which the university could learn. However, with the visitation of Professor Omar Hassan Kasule to the University, he was able to give them his experience from the International Islamic University, Malaysia (IIUM) and this helped the University to move in the proper direction. The Vice-Chancellor also confirmed several other academic linkages with other universities and their impacts on his university. This experience informs that efforts need to be channeled towards linking up the universities with regional and international partner institutions to address concerns at national and global levels. Part of the challenges facing the universities could however be overcome if right from the beginning, such universities had taken a step toward internationalization. This can be in the form of having cooperative ties with some universities in Muslim countries.

Opportunities for collaboration and partnership for need-based interactive efforts with the collective wisdom of professionals will help in no small measure in collaborating with international educational bodies for partnership in terms of staff development and gaining access to funding agencies. Renowned international organizations like UNESCO, ISESCO, and WAMY can also come to the aid of these universities if properly internationalized.

Internationalization will also assist Muslim universities in Nigeria to identify and interact with other universities and higher learning institutions of Muslim countries that are highly ranked in quality of education and other aspects. A network of these universities and institutions would assist Muslim universities in Nigeria to have a high sense of competing with other universities in terms of infrastructure, equipment and materials so that the competencies and capacities of these institutions become at par with other leading universities of the world.

The adoption of internationalization will also assist Muslim universities in Nigeria to forge ahead of others and will also raise the standard and quality of the students through student exchange programmes. In addition, this will create an opportunity for the awarding of fellowships and grants to staff of the universities, while students can also enjoy scholarships.

It is pertinent to mention that Muslim universities need to adopt internationalization for Islamization of the knowledge programme. It is believed that knowledge is universal, and so what is obtainable in one country or environment is possible to be obtainable in another country. Where there are divergences if any, a comparison could be made through internationalization as there is an opportunity for international consortia and collaboration among universities. The

spirit of internationalization assisted the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto in its manpower training when it sent some staff of the University from the Department of Economics to the International Islamic University, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia to be trained up to Master's degree level. Three other members of staff from Islamic Studies, Education and Economics were also sent to Sains University Malaysia to be trained up to doctoral degree level (Adebayo, 2003). Through this as well, King Abdulaziz University and the International Islamic University Islamabad have assisted the programme of Islamization of UDUS by supervising the Ph D theses of the University's members of staff recruited for it. The candidates were allowed to go and attend lectures and meet their foreign supervisors at King Abdulaziz University and this afforded them access to experts as well as the latest research works in their areas of study.

Since knowledge is seen as a lost property of the Muslims which they are expected to pick wherever they get it, Muslim universities can equally collaborate with conventional universities or universities other than from the Muslim world. This will assist in showcasing Islamic values to those universities. By implication, the teaching of Islam can be facilitated within different cultures. In that wise, Islamic subjects can be taught in diverse languages and not through Arabic alone.

One other means that Muslim universities could internationalize their programmes is by partnering with renowned universities abroad to contribute to national and global development in science and technology. This method was adopted by the University of Science and Technology, Ifaki-Ekiti (USTI) which partners with one of the top ten universities in the world based in Korea, Kyungnam University to establish a Centre for Minerals Testing (Okebukola, 2010).

According to Okebukola (2010), the Institution also partners with the National Agency for Science and Engineering Infrastructure (NASENI) to establish "a state-of-the-art nanotechnology laboratory with well-trained personnel to prepare its students in the modern art of nanotechnology." In addition, USTI is said to have concluded partnering with top offshore IT training institutes in the US, UK, India and Nigeria to facilitate the enrolment of all students of the institution for ICT courses leading to obtaining professional certificates before graduation.

Challenges facing internationalization of Muslim universities

One of the major challenges facing Muslim universities is the lack of funds which makes it virtually impossible to execute their highly demanding educational projects. Durosaro (2012) identifies several factors that contribute to the rising burden of the cost of education in Nigeria generally. Such include increases in staff salaries and allowances, procurement of modern educational technology and provision of municipal services and infrastructures by institutions, among others. With particular reference to private universities in Nigeria, Oloyede and Adekola (2010) observe that "running a university requires a large capital outlay and a massive injection of funds" that many of these institutions had to gasp for breath before graduating their first set of students. While some of these universities are busy addressing the multifarious challenges facing them, little attention is paid to internalizing their programmes.

The process of integrating international perspectives in Muslim universities is too cumbersome for a leader who is not a visionary. Internationalization could therefore hardly be possible in the hands of a leader who does not have a flair for multi-dimensional external changes in global realities.

Another major obstacle to internationalization is the attitude of some Muslim universities towards science and technology. Most of the Muslim universities only concentrate on courses that are market-driven and require less investment in terms of infrastructure and equipment. Investment in technological, medical and professional courses will no doubt assist these universities in the process of internationalization; the absence of these programmes in the universities no doubt hampers internationalization there.

One of the major challenges facing Muslim universities in the internationalization process is the fear of brain drain that may arise from it. Experience has shown that some universities which send their staff out of their universities for further studies eventually lose them to some other universities abroad. Such staff may decide to stay abroad, and when they come back home, they resume to another university with a better offer. Private universities that send out their staff therefore risk the chance of losing such staff to public universities with better offers.

Recommendation and Conclusion

For any effective Islamization and internationalization programme, Muslim universities in Nigeria must rise to the task of having effective and reliable internet services. This will help in no small measure in showcasing and promoting universities offshore.

The exchange of academic staff and students is required for Islamization and internalization. There is no doubt that some international Islamic universities have gone far in the Islamization of knowledge programme. Exchanging staff and students with those institutions will facilitate further understanding of the programme. To start with, this can be done in the form of inviting prominent scholars and professors in the field of Islamization for lectures and

conferences or sponsoring staff to such related conferences. Muslim universities in Nigeria should make efforts to link themselves worldwide by organizing brilliant international events and as well enlarge the number of transnational academics.

Muslim universities should also make it a matter of serious priority to improve research collaboration not only with institutions but also with companies and industries. This effort will facilitate the cross-fertilization of ideas amongst scholars and attract new partnerships.

Muslim universities in Nigeria should come together under one umbrella body. In other words, they should come up with a common policy and cooperate within the framework of the Islamic world. Special consideration should be given to the Islamization work plan of al-Faruqi with a view to domesticating them and mapping out a strategy for achieving the Islamization goals for which these Muslim universities were established.

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